

IMIA - Medical Concept Representation WG

- business meeting @ MEDINFO 2013, Aug 23, Copenhagen -
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Summary

Why?

The business meeting was called by the new leadership and the active members of the WG in order to revitalize the working group as a whole – regarding all aspects.

Who?

Participants were invited by social media (relevant LinkedIn groups), by the merits for earlier activities and by having relevant publications at MEDINFO 2013. The invitation was open and it was re-posted to well over 200 interested parties. Finally 18 participants and an additional set of 7 persons with an interest in participating actively were registered.

What it is About?

We discussed the potential scope, domain and the vision from the WG. We have identified a set of conceivable actions for the interested members. Our [recent survey and bibliometric study](#) published at MEDINFO 2013 showed that there is a paradigm shift from “concept representation” to a very wide area stretching from understanding and using medical natural language towards knowledge representation, ontologies and other formal tools, including the broad world of medical terminology systems. The WG should respond to this change. We agreed to deal with the overall scientific area of biomedical semantics – including the natural language domain as there is no other IMIA WG to deal with this broad territory. The WG should not focus on particular technologies or tools as e.g. ontologies. We should make clear however what are the pieces of the knowledge representation puzzle in biomedicine and how they fit together, to take a look at biomedical ontology/NLP “in action”. The goal would be connecting the users, appliers of knowledge representation tools and methods with the theorists and developers. We should show what the pieces of the puzzle are, making them more visible and easier to be consolidated.

What to Deliver?

Suggestions were made to reach out to interested partners with a limited set of *services*

- to the community: (1) publish a regular list of most influential papers in the field, use the Yearbook and other fora, (2) organize regular meetings/workshops at major conferences (?) to bring together interested parties, minimal program: a workshop at 2015 MEDINFO, endorse, sponsor domain related meetings organized by other parties (ICBO, etc) (3) facilitate bilateral visits, gathering hands-on experience by a list of available hosts, good practice sites
- to IMIA: participate in the programming of the biomedical knowledge representation domain, involvement in the relevant conference program and editorial committees,
- to the academic world: curriculum development, guidance for our domain. (Comment: participation in the IMIA accreditation work could be one of the solutions).

Delivery tools / workbench are the LinkedIn group and the Wiki site:

- http://www.linkedin.com/groups?gid=3680642&trk=my_groups-b-grp-v
- <http://imia-mcr-wg.wikispaces.com/IMIA+MCR+WG+home+page#!>

Action Points:

Participants agreed on a tentative list of action points, as (1) reaching out, (2) meeting reporting (3) preparation of a WG Workshop at **MEDINFO 2015** (4) **inquiring at IMIA regarding participation in relevant programming and involvement in relevant editorial work / committees**, (5) report the results of this preparatory work till the end of this year. WG members are expected to suggest (1) influential papers / works / projects to be shared with the community, (2) willingness to host meetings, (3) to host / welcome visitors presenting their work in the domain of medical semantic (4) to suggest the involvement of other parties / industry to WG activities, (5) doing a semiformal survey to collect the data on previously suggested activities – see the detailed report below.

A New Name for the Working Group - Motion on Renaming the WG

The results of the MCR WG survey and bibliometric study indicated that the name “Medical Concept Representation” does not cover the desired broad coverage of the domain of medical semantics in the literature. The reasons for changing the working group name might be summarized as: we need (1) to cover “representation” in a broader sense, (2) differentiated subjects of representations: clinical reality, information items, word meanings should be covered, we realize that (1) the ambiguity of the word “concept” did not dwindle over time and (2) we have to go back to the roots: NLP was in the scope of this group in the first two decades. New names proposed: (1) Language and Meaning for Health (LMH), **most voted** (2) **“Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (LaMB)”**, (3) Health Terminologies, Ontologies and Semantics (HTOS), (4) Vocabularies, Ontologies, Language (VOL), (5) Terminologies, Ontologies, Language (TOL), (6) Representation of Meaning (RoM), (7) Representational Structures for Health (RSH), (8) Representing and Understanding Biomedical Knowledge (RUBiK),

Participants agreed to propose **“Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (LaMB)”** for consideration to the members¹ of the working group.

See the full report here:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?gid=3680642&trk=my_groups-b-grp-v
<http://imia-mcr-wg.wikispaces.com/IMIA+MCR+WG+home+page#!>

¹ Membership to the Working Group is open. We consider members of the LinkedIn group and the actively responding / reacting / participating authors of relevant MEDINFO papers as a starting set.